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UDK: 347.633(4-672EU)
UDK: 316.362.31(4-672EU)
UDK: 342.726-053.2
UDK: 341.231.14-053.2

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17813176

ZASNIVANJE JEDNORODITELJSKE PORODICE USVOJENJEM

Zbog restriktivnih pravila o usvajanju, kao i uskog kruga lica kojima je dozvoljeno da se nađu u ulozi usvojioca, značajan broj dece ostaje bez porodičnog doma, čekajući godinama na usvojenje. Postoji potreba za reformom zakonske regulative i proširenjem kruga lica koja mogu postati usvojioci, čime bi se povećale šanse za usvojenje dece. Poslednjih godina svedoci smo značajnog porasta broja jednoroditeljskih porodica. Zasnivanje jednoroditeljske porodice dodatno je olakšano omogućavanjem pristupa biomedicinski potpomognutoj oplodnji ženama koje nemaju partnera. U svetlu ovih promena, ni usvojenje ne bi trebalo biti ograničeno samo na lica koja se nalaze u braku ili vanbračnoj zajednici. Svako ko želi da pruži detetu ljubav i dom zaslužuje priliku da postane roditelj, bez obzira na bračni status. Ovaj rad analizira savremene pravne tendencije u oblasti usvojenja dece, sa posebnim naglaskom na proširenje kruga lica koja mogu biti usvojioci. Polazeći od načela najboljeg interesa deteta, autor razmatra opravdanost uključivanja samaca u kategoriju potencijalnih usvojlaca, pri čemu ukazuje na dominantne tokove u uporednom pravu.

Ključne reči: usvojlac, usvojenik, najbolji interes deteta, uslovi za usvojenje na strani usvojioca, jednoroditeljska porodica.

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ESTABLISHING A SINGLE-PARENT FAMILY THROUGH ADOPTION

Due to restrictive adoption regulations and the narrow circle of individuals permitted to assume the role of adoptive parents, a significant number of children remain without a family home, often waiting for years to be adopted. In order to increase the chances for successful adoption of children, there is a pressing need for reform in the legal framework governing adoption, and for an expansion of the pool of individuals eligible to become adoptive parents. In recent years, we have observed a notable rise in the number of single-parent families. The establishment of these families has been further facilitated by allowing access to assisted reproductive technologies for women without partners. In light of these developments, adoption should not be confined solely to individuals who are married or live in a cohabiting relationship. Anyone who wishes to provide a child with love and a supportive home deserves the opportunity to become a parent, irrespective of their marital status. This paper analyzes the contemporary legal trends in the area of child adoption, with specific reference to the expansion of the circle of individuals eligible to become adoptive parents. Drawing upon the principle of the best interests of the child, the author examines the justification for including single individuals in the category of potential adoptive parents, while highlighting the prevailing trends in comparative law.

Keywords: adoptive parent, adoptee, best interest of the child, adoption requirements for the adoptive parent, single-parent family.